

Spectrophotometric Determination of Iridium(IV) with Propionyl Promazine Phosphate

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A simple, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of iridium(IV). The method is based on the formation of a red coloured radical cation by Ir^{IV} with propionyl promazine phosphate in perchloric acid medium. The radical cation exhibits the absorption maximum at 515 nm. Beer's law is obeyed for Ir^{IV} in the range 0.2–26 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $9.25 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.02 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{ Ir}^{\text{IV}}$, respectively, at 515 nm. The colour reaction is free from interference of Rh, Pd, Pt, Os, base metals and a number of anions. The method has been applied for the determination of Ir^{IV} in synthetic mixtures corresponding to osmiridium alloy.

IRIDIUM is one of the minor constituents in most platinum metals deposits. It is commonly used in jewelry, electrical contacts which operate at high currents and corrosion-resistant chemical wares. Because of its commercial importance a wide variety of chromogenic reagents have been proposed for the determination of Ir^{1,2}. In most of these systems, the preliminary separation of platinum metals, particularly the most closely associated rhodium is necessary before its determination.

During the course of our investigations on the analytical applications of phenothiazines³⁻⁹, it was found that iridium(IV) reacts with propionyl promazine phosphate (PPP), 1-[10-[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]phenothiazine-2-yl]-1-propanone phosphate, to form a red coloured radical cation, which is stable in acidic solution. This paper describes the application of this reaction for spectrophotometric determination of iridium(IV) without separation of Pd, Pt, Rh and Os.

Experimental

A Beckman DB spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells was used for absorbance measurements.

A stock solution of iridium(IV) was prepared by dissolving ammonium chloroiridate (Johnson Matthey) (1 g) in dilute hydrochloric acid and diluting to volume in a 250 ml standard flask with 1 M HCl and standardised gravimetrically by precipitating iridium as 2-mercaptobenzothiazole complex¹. A 50 ppm iridium(IV) solution was prepared by further dilution with 1 M HCl. An aqueous 0.2% solution of propionyl promazine phosphate was prepared and stored in a refrigerator. All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade unless otherwise mentioned.

Procedure: To the test solution, containing 5–650 μg of iridium(IV) in a 25 ml standard flask,

10 M HClO₄ (5 ml) and 0.2% PPP (1 ml) were added. The solution was diluted to volume with water, mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 515 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Optical conditions for the formation of radical cation: It has been found that iridium(IV) reacts with PPP at room temperature (27°) in mineral acid medium to form a red coloured species, which is believed to be a radical cation. The nature of the radical was found by passing an aliquot of the red coloured solution through the cation-exchange resin Amberlite IR-120(H). The complete absorption of the colour by the ion-exchanger has indicated that the radical is cationic.

Effect of acids: Maximum and constant absorbance values are obtained instantaneously after adding the reagent to iridium(IV) solution in 0.5–3.0 M HClO₄ and remain stable for 40 min. Below 0.5 M acid concentration, the colour development is slow, and at concentration higher than 3.0 M, the reagent is slowly oxidised. Though the red coloured radical cation is also formed in the presence of HCl, H₂SO₄, HNO₃ or H₃PO₄ medium, the absorbance readings do not remain stable for more than 5 min in these acids. Perchloric acid was chosen as the reaction medium because of the stability of the radical cation and less interference from other platinum metals.

Effect of amounts of reagent: In a 25 ml of final solution, 0.5–2.0 ml of 0.2% PPP solution gives maximum absorbance with 10 ppm of iridium(IV). Hence, the use of 1 ml of the reagent solution is recommended.

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectra of the reagent blank, iridium(IV) solution and radical cation against the reagent blank have been measured

over the range 400–580 nm. The absorption maximum of the radical cation is at 515 nm at which the reagent absorbs negligibly (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (1) reagent blank, (2) Ir^{IV} solution against reagent blank and (3) iridium-PPP radical cation against reagent blank. Ir^{IV}, 10 ppm and perchloric acid, 2 M.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, sensitivity and photometric error: Beer's law is obeyed over the range 0.2–26 ppm of iridium(IV). The molar absorptivity is $9.25 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity is $0.020 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{ Ir}^{\text{IV}}$ at 515 nm. For 10 parallel determinations of 10 ppm of iridium, the relative error and standard deviation were found to be 0.8% and 0.022, respectively.

Effect of foreign ions: Synthetic solutions containing 10 ppm of iridium(IV) and varying amounts of foreign ions were prepared and the iridium was determined. The following amounts (ppm) of foreign ions have been found to give less than 2% error: Ru^{III} (6), Rh^{III} (100), Os^{VIII} (120), Pt^{IV} (250), Au^{III} (1), Ag^I (25), Fe^{III} (25), Co^{II} (700), Ni^{II} (400), Cu^{II} (1800), Pb^{II} (1200), Cr^{III} (600), U^{VI} (2500), fluoride (10000), chloride (10000), bromide (3000), nitrate (5000), sulphate (10000), phosphate (5000), acetate (5000), oxalate (10000), tartrate (10000), citrate (10000) and EDTA (12000). A 12-fold excess (120 ppm) of Pd^{II} has been tolerated in the presence of EDTA as masking agent. Interferences due to gold can be eliminated by extraction with ethyl acetate¹ and ruthenium by

distillation as tetroxide¹ before the determination of iridium.

Determination of iridium in osmiridium alloy, electrical contacts and synthetic matrices: Synthetic mixtures corresponding to osmiridium alloy containing 20% Ir and 80% Os, electrical contacts containing 10% Ir and 90% Pt and synthetic mixtures containing varying amounts of Ir, Pd, Pt and Rh, were prepared and the Ir content was determined following the recommended procedure. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF IRIDIUM(IV) IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES CORRESPONDING TO OSMIRIDIUM ALLOY, ELECTRICAL CONTACTS AND IN THE SYNTHETIC MATRICES

Osmiridium alloy					
Ir ^{IV} taken ppm	Os ^{VIII} added ppm	Ir ^{IV} found* ppm	Relative standard deviation		
10	40	9.92	0.022		
15	60	14.85	0.018		
20	80	19.80	0.016		
Electrical contacts					
Ir ^{IV} taken ppm	Pt ^{IV} added ppm	Ir ^{IV} found* ppm	Relative standard deviation		
10	90	10.05	0.024		
15	135	15.10	0.020		
20	180	20.15	0.018		
Synthetic matrices containing platinum metals					
Ir ^{IV} taken ppm	Pd ^{II} **	Pt ^{IV} added ppm	Rh ^{III}	Ir ^{IV} found* ppm	Relative standard deviation
10	50	50	50	10.04	0.026
15	75	75	75	15.08	0.022
20	100	100	100	20.20	0.016

* Mean value of six determinations. ** Used 5 ml of 10% EDTA as masking agent.

Comparison with other methods: Most of the reagents reported in recent years for the spectrophotometric determination of Ir require either heating on a water-bath for various intervals or prior extraction of the complex with organic solvents, making the procedure more tedious and time consuming. The method described here is one of the most simple and compares favourably with others for the spectrophotometric determination of iridium(IV).

The tolerance of the proposed method to a large number of cations and anions is fairly good. A particular advantage of the proposed method is that PPP can be used for the determination of Ir in the presence of 10-fold excess of Rh, 12-fold excess of Pd and Os and 25-fold excess of Pt without prior separation.

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